

INFLUENCE OF GRAPHENE SIZE AND CONTENT
ON THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF NOVEL
POLY(LACTIC) ACID NANOCOMPOSITES

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Abstract

In this work, nanocomposites of poly(lactic) acid incorporating two kinds of highly thermal conductive graphene nanoplatelets differing in size and purity were fabricated by melt extrusion. Nanocomposites of 1.5–9 wt% filler contents were characterized using thermal constant analysis, X-ray diffraction and infrared spectroscopy to clarify their functionality, related to composition and morphology. The thermal conductivity increases linearly with increasing the filler concentration, but it is essentially determined by the size and purity of fillers and thermal interfacial resistance.

Key words: PLA, graphene nanoplatelets, thermal conductivity, WAXD, FT-IR

Introduction. Polymers are usually characterized by very low thermal conductivity (0.1–0.5 W/m.K), which is strongly affected by the complex polymer morphology, crystallinity, molecular orientation, etc. [1]. Enhancing the thermal conductivity of polymers is important for many applications and recently this has become a strategic research topic. The graphene-based polymer composites are expected to provide superior thermal conductivity, due to the exceptional thermal properties of graphene, which is among the highest of any known material [2]. The

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properties of nanocomposites obviously depend on many factors, but the good dispersion, the network connectivity of nanofillers and the polymer-filler interactions are found of major importance for production of electrically conductive and mechanically strong PLA composites for 3D printing [3]. In our previous studies, the incorporation of graphene nanoplatelets and carbon nanotubes in poly(lactic) acid was found to enhance significantly the thermal and electrical conductivity through the polymer, where the effect of graphene on thermal conductivity is much stronger than that of carbon nanotubes [4,5]. Thermal conductive polymer micro-composites with graphite are studied highly filled, to 80 wt% [6], which limited their application in 3D printing. However, systematic studies are needed to understand the effects of the essential graphene characteristics, volume fraction and interfacial interactions in order to obtain polymer nanocomposites with enhanced and controllable thermal conductivity.

The aim of the present study is to estimate the influence of the filler concentration, the size and the dispersion of graphene nanoplatelets on thermal conductivity of poly(lactic) acid polymer. Two commercial grades (GNP and IGNP) are used to produce nanocomposites with varying filler content. The crystallite size and dispersion of graphene nanoplatelets, as well as the intrinsic interactions were analyzed and associated with the enhancement of thermal conductivity of composites.

Experimental. Ingeo™ Biopolymer PLA-3D850 with MFR 7–9 g/10 min (210 °C, 2.16 kg) was purchased from Nature Works, USA. Two grades of graphene (from Times Nano Co., China) were used: Industrial graphene nanoplatelets (IGNP) with purity 90% (incl. 10% carbon black impurities); number of layers < 30, thickness < 4–30 nm, diameter (2–16 μm), aspect ratio (AR = 240); and Graphene nanoplatelets (GNP) with purity 99.5%, number of layers < 20, thickness < 4–20 nm, mean diameter (5–10 μm), aspect ratio (AR = 500). Both fillers have non-functionalized surfaces with specific surface area of 30–40 m²/g. The nanocomposites with filler contents 1.5–9 wt% were fabricated by melt extrusion using the twin screw extruder COLLIN Teach-Line ZK25T, with a screw speed 40 rpm at $T = 170$ – 190 °C. A Hot Disk 2500 thermal constant analyzer (Hot Disk Inc., Göteborg, Sweden) was used to measure the thermal conductivity through a transient plane source method. The sensor supplied a heat pulse of 0.01 W for 40 s to the sample and the change in temperature was recorded. Wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) was performed by DX-1000 X-ray diffractometer (Dandong Fangyuan Instrument) employing Copper Line Focus X-ray tube, producing $K\alpha$ radiation by a generator operating at 45 kV and 25 mA. The diffraction patterns of pressed films were undertaken in the range from 5 °C to 70 °C at a rate of 1 °C/min. The WAXD data were processed using the MDI Jade software capable of analyzing the crystal structure of materials. The FT-IR spectra in the scanning range from 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹, was determined by KBr technique with a Nicolet 6700 spectrometer.

Fig. 1. Thermal conductivity vs. filler content of PLA nanocomposites incorporating two kinds of graphene nanoplatelets, IGNP and GNP

Results and discussion. The thermal conductivity with increasing filler contents from 1.5 to 9 wt% is presented in Fig. 1 for the PLA nanocomposites with the two kinds of graphene nanoplatelets, IGNP and GNP. In general, the conductivity of composites increases almost linearly by increasing the filler content, compared to the neat PLA. Therefore, the concentration dependence of the thermal conductivity is not percolated [2, 7] in this filler content range, in contrast to the electrical percolation of the same composites, that was determined around 3–6 wt% [4]. Importantly, the nanocomposites containing IGNP fillers show higher thermal conductivity values compared to those with GNPs.

Thus an enhancement of 254% is observed for 9 wt% IGNP/PLA (0.73 W/m.K), corresponding to 223% for 9 wt% GNP/PLA (0.66 W/m.K), if compared to the neat PLA (0.2 W/m.K). This means more effective thermal flow between the IGNP surfaces, probably due to the larger polydispersity of diameter and large amount of carbon black impurities, or lower solid-liquid interfacial thermal resistance, compared to the GNPs. Researchers measured the thermal conductivity of graphene in the range 3000–5000 W/m.K at room temperature, compared with the thermal conductivity of pyrolytic graphite of approximately $2000 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$ [2]. However, the addition of 1.5–9 wt% of graphene nanoplatelets to the PLA matrix does not influence so much the thermal conductivity of nanocomposites. Therefore, the thermal interface resistance (Kapitza's resistance) could play a significant role in heat conduction of polymer nanocomposites, due to the high surface area of nanofillers.

Fig. 2. Diffraction patterns of: (a) IGNP/PLA and (b) GNP/PLA with varying filler content, compared to the neat PLA and the two filler kinds

In order to clarify the role of the size and dispersion of graphene platelets as well as the effect of interfaces on thermal conductivity of PLA nanocomposites, we focus on X-ray diffraction analysis (WAXD) of the filler powder and nanocomposites. Figure 2 presents the diffraction patterns of (a) IGNP/PLA and (b) GNP/PLA with varying filler contents, as compared to the spectra of the filler powders and PLA. As seen, the position of the (002) reflection falls at almost the same angle value of $2\theta = 26.25^\circ$ for IGNP (Fig. 2a), and $2\theta = 26.27^\circ$ for GNP (Fig. 2b). For nanocomposites, the peak (002) is almost insufficiently shifted to slightly higher 2θ values by increasing the filler content compared to that of the powders (Table 1). The wide halo at $2\theta = 15.3^\circ$ observed for nanocomposites is associated with the amorphous PLA phase.

The diffraction patterns in Fig. 2 were processed using MDI Jade software to determine the crystallite size of the stacking graphene platelets and the results are summarized in Table 1. The Bragg's equation was applied to (002) reflection for evaluating the distance between graphene layers, $d(002) = \lambda / (2 \sin \theta)$, where λ is the wavelength of the incident X-rays and θ is the angle of reflection [8]. The values of 3.38–3.39 Å are obtained for the graphene nanoplatelets interlayer distance of both nanocomposites and powders, respectively, thus confirming the absence of intercalation or exfoliation of platelets in nanocomposites. The average height of two-dimensional graphene platelets in the plane of layer, L_{hkl} , denoted as L_c or (H) is calculated, as reported elsewhere [8,9], using the Scherrer equation, $L_{hkl} = k\lambda / (\beta_{hkl} \cos \theta)$, where: β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the (002) reflection, with the shape factor $k = 0.9$ [9]. The results are summarized in Table 1. The average height L_c (H) of the stacking graphene platelets was obtained of 16.5 nm for the IGNP powder, while larger height $H = 21.5$ nm was calculated for the GNP powder.

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Interplaner distance (d) and average height (H) of stacked graphene platelets, related to thermal conductivity of nanocomposites

Sample	Peak (002)				λ [W/m.K]
	2θ [deg]	d [Å]	FWHM [deg]	$L_c(H)$ [nm]	
IGNP	26.25	3.392	0.505	16.5	–
1.5% IGNP/PLA	26.31	3.383	0.339	25.2	0.293
3% IGNP/PLA	26.30	3.382	0.229	39.7	0.375
6% IGNP/PLA	26.29	3.378	0.262	33.7	0.550
9% IGNP/PLA	26.32	3.379	0.296	29.3	0.726
GNP	26.27	3.389	0.390	21.5	–
1.5% GNP/PLA	26.28	3.385	0.339	24.3	0.262
3% GNP/PLA	26.30	3.384	0.229	28.1	0.330
6% GNP/PLA	26.33	3.378	0.262	29.3	0.484
9% GNP/PLA	26.33	3.385	0.296	26.1	0.662
Neat PLA	–				0.205

If we consider the nanocomposites, the average height of graphene nanoplatelets in the nanocomposites is higher than that of powders. This is due to the ability of graphene nanoplatelets to easily interact, forming agglomerates and a percolated network structure that is a result from Van der Waals attraction forces between the graphite layers, which are stronger than the interactions between graphene nanoplatelets and the polymer. Importantly, the stacking graphene nanostructures in IGNP/PLA are found of larger height (~ 25 – 40 nm) compared to that in GNP/PLA nanocomposites (~ 24 – 29 nm). This may be associated with a stronger particle-particle interactions of IGNP platelets in the PLA matrix compared to slightly weaker interactions of GNPs. Moreover, the graphite height increases ungradually by increasing the filler concentration, obviously due to different degree of dispersion of nanocomposites. This confirms the uncontrolled dispersion of filler in the PLA matrix during processing.

For nanocomposites, weak interfacial polymer-filler interactions may lead to insufficient transport of phonons through the interface that is the so-called interfacial thermal resistance (Kapitza's resistance of an interface boundary). This may be predicted by a model for the effective thermal conductivity of an individual particle (λ_f^*) in a composite [10]: $\lambda_f^* = \lambda_f / (1 + R_k \lambda_f / d)$, where λ_f is the thermal conductivity of a particle, R_k is the interphase resistance and d is the particle size. If we consider the anisotropic shape of the graphene platelets with nanoscale height ($H \sim 24$ – 40 nm) and micron-scale diameter (2 – 16 μm), using this equation one may predict an anisotropic thermal conductivity of graphene in nanocomposites. Thus, for the heat conduction in the direction parallel to the diameter of graphene platelets the interfacial resistance is not important, since $R_k/H \rightarrow 0$, so $\lambda_f^* \rightarrow \lambda_f$, thus the conductivity of the composite depends on

the thermal conductivity of the filler. However, for the heat transfer through the height of the platelet (i.e. perpendicular to the diameter) the filler is not so strongly involved in the thermal conductivity, as the value of $R_k/H \rightarrow \infty$, so $\lambda_f^* \rightarrow 0$. As the heat conduction in our study is measured perpendicular to the direction of the alignment of graphene in pressed nanocomposite samples, the model predictions confirm the experimental results that the graphene content, assisted by the larger height of IGNP platelets will produce higher thermal conductivity than that of thinner GNPs in the nanocomposites. The presence of 10% carbon black impurities in IGNP obviously assists in enhancing the conductivity.

In order to assess the interfacial polymer-filler interactions, Fig. 3 presents the FT-IR spectra in the scanning range from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} for IGNP, GNP, PLA and their 6 wt% nanocomposites. In Fig. 3a and b, the characteristic bands of IGNP and GNP appear at the same wavenumbers, corresponding to stretching vibrations of CH- group at 2854 cm^{-1} and 2925 cm^{-1} . The bands at 3432–3428 cm^{-1} , 1631–1653 cm^{-1} , 1110–1112 cm^{-1} and 1045–1058 cm^{-1} are due to stretching vibrations of the –OH, C=O and C–O adsorption groups, respectively. The characteristic bands of both kinds graphene nanoplatelets are typical of non-functionalized surfaces and therefore they contribute insufficiently to the interfacial interactions.

By comparing the spectra of both fillers and nanocomposites in Fig. 3 a,b, it is noticed that the peaks characteristics for the fillers are not present in the spectrum of composite materials, which is probably due to their low concentration. While the composite materials containing 6% filler demonstrate spectra with peaks, which coincide with the frequency of the vibration bands of the pure PLA. It follows that no new bonds are formed between the filler and the polymer, such

Fig. 3. IR spectra of (a) Industrial IGNP and 6 wt% IGNP/PLA, as well as (b) GNP and 6 wt% GNP/PLA nanocomposites, compared to PLA

as hydrogen bonding or direct interaction of a specified group and the adsorption site of the liquid matrix. For instance, the usual effects of hydrogen bonding on the stretching and the deformation bands, leading to shift of the peaks towards lower or higher frequencies, respectively, are missing in both systems IGNP/PLA and GNP/PLA, obviously due to the absence of surface functionalization of both fillers. Therefore, similar and high interfacial thermal resistance (Kapitza's resistance) is expected in both composites.

Conclusions. Two commercial grades of graphene nanoplatelets (GNP and IGNP) with different size of plates were used to produce PLA nanocomposites of 1.5 to 9 wt% filler contents. Thermal conductivity was observed to increase linearly by increasing the filler contents. The IGNP/PLA nanocomposites produce higher conductivity, compared to GNP/PLA, which was associated with larger size and polydispersity of IGNP platelets compared to those of GNPs. Due to the anisotropic shape and the nanoscale height of graphene platelets, the thermal transfer in alignment direction depends mainly on the filler size, while perpendicular to the alignment of layers, the filler is not so strongly involved in the thermal conduction. The degree of dispersion, filler content and particle-particle interactions enhance thermal conductivity. The interfacial thermal resistance was proposed to be similar for both kinds of fillers due to weak interfacial interactions and the absence of filler surface functionalization. The nanocomposites are studied for 3D printing applications.

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